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Research Design Essay

Artificial Intelligence and Regulatory Enforcement: A Comparative Research Design of Tax Administrations in Argentina, Brazil, Estonia, and the Netherlands

Abstract

Tax authorities across the world are adopting artificial intelligence systems to decide whom to audit, yet enforcement theory was built on assumptions about human interaction that these systems disrupt. This research design studies how AI reshapes the regulator-regulatee relationship through four tax administrations with different levels of algorithmic deployment and institutional oversight: ARCA in Argentina, Receita Federal in Brazil, the Estonian Tax and Customs Board, and the Dutch Belastingdienst. The central hypothesis is that AI's effect on enforcement posture is not uniform but mediated by institutional oversight. The design combines within-case process tracing with structured cross-case comparison, supported by primary sources. The work contributes a bridge between classic enforcement theory and algorithmic governance, a comparative approach with two Latin American and two European cases, and practical implications for sequencing AI adoption, identifying institutional pressure points, and designing evaluable reforms.

1. Introduction

In October 2024 Argentina replaced the AFIP with ARCA through Decree 953/2024, announcing the dismissal of 3,155 employees (~15% of staff) and a mandate to intensify artificial intelligence in tax enforcement. The plan was partially halted by the National Labour Court of Appeals in January 2025, illustrating the institutional tension this work seeks to theorise. In Brazil, Receita Federal reported in 2025 the detection of R\$ 11 billion in evasion assisted by AI and, in February 2026, issued a formal AI policy with human-oversight safeguards (Portaria RFB 647/2026). Estonia's Tax and Customs Board has used machine learning to detect underreported income since around 2014, with risk scores visible to taxpayers through a colour-coded system. In February 2020 the District Court of The Hague ordered the suspension of the Dutch SyRI system for violating Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights, in one of the first global rulings against an algorithmic public-enforcement system.

These episodes share a central feature: AI is reshaping the relationship between regulators and regulatees in tax administration. Classic enforcement theory (Ayres and Braithwaite, 1992; Scholz, 1984) assumes human interactions marked by discretion, mutual observation, and iterative adjustment. Algorithmic governance literature (Coglianese and Lehr, 2017; Yeung, 2018) focuses on legality and transparency but pays less attention to how AI alters the enforcement logic that classic theory described. Tax authorities are therefore investing in these tools without an explicit theory of how they transform their relationship with taxpayers.

The central question of this essay is: does the adoption of AI-based risk-scoring tools by regulatory enforcement agencies shift the regulator-regulatee relationship toward deterrence-based or persuasion-based enforcement, and with what consequences for compliance?

The essay is organised in four sections: a targeted literature review, the theoretical framework and hypotheses, the methodological design, and a conclusion with practical implications and future research lines.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Regulatory enforcement: deterrence and persuasion

Contemporary enforcement theory is organised around a tension between two logics. Deterrence assumes that firms will try to evade regulation and requires credible sanctions to achieve compliance. Persuasion assumes that firms are in principle willing to comply and privileges dialogue, education, and cooperation (Tombs and Whyte, 2013).

The most influential synthesis is Ayres and Braithwaite's (1992) responsive regulation pyramid: the regulator begins with persuasion and gradually escalates to increasing sanctions only when cooperation fails. Scholz (1984) formalised this intuition as a tit-for-tat game where conditional cooperation produces better outcomes than confrontation, provided the regulator can observe the firm's behaviour and respond proportionally.

These theories share three implicit assumptions: that the regulator is a human agent exercising case-by-case discretion; that firms hold informational advantages, making cooperative information extraction necessary (Tombs and Whyte, 2013); and that the regulator-regulatee relationship is an iterative game with mutually observable signals (Scholz, 1984). All three were built in a world without algorithmic systems, and all three are altered when AI enters the scene.

2.2 Algorithmic governance

A parallel literature examines AI in public administration. Coglianese and Lehr (2017) argue that machine learning in government agencies can be compatible with administrative law, while Coglianese (2021) holds that algorithms can serve traditional public-administration values, albeit with a distinctive challenge around empathy.

Yeung (2018) introduces a distinction central to this study: adaptive algorithmic regulation (machine-learning systems that learn and adjust) versus prescriptive regulation (codified rules applied automatically). Argentine systems lean toward the prescriptive pole, while Estonian systems lean toward the adaptive. Van Bekkum and Zuiderveen Borgesius (2021) show, through the SyRI case, how a system deployed without sufficient safeguards violated fundamental rights. The Dutch case is important because SyRI was deployed largely in low-income neighbourhoods, while the parallel toeslagenaffaire wrongly flagged tens of thousands of families, mostly with migrant backgrounds, as benefit fraudsters, leading to the resignation of the Rutte government in January 2021. These consequences explain the density of the current Dutch oversight framework.

This literature shares a common orientation: the analysis of legality, transparency, and fundamental rights. It addresses whether AI systems are compatible with normative frameworks but not how they reconfigure the incentives and relationships at the core of classic enforcement theory.

2.3 Recent empirical work

Empirical studies are abundant but fragmented. A recent International Growth Centre study on Indian tax administration found that machine-learning models accurately identify ghost firms but do not necessarily increase enforcement outcomes, pointing to bottlenecks in human follow-up capacity. For Latin America, Verrastro (2025), through the Centre for Tax Administration Studies at UBA, documents predictive models in Argentina's tax authority, one of the few academic sources on the Argentine case.

Three limitations in this literature motivate the present work: studies tend to be single-country with strong OECD bias; they rarely connect empirical findings to enforcement theory; and institutional variation is undertheorised.

2.4 The gap and the contribution

The three bodies of literature converge on the object of study but do not speak to each other. This work connects them. Theoretically, it contrasts the assumptions of classic enforcement theory with the effects of AI systems. Methodologically, it incorporates two Latin American cases alongside two European ones, correcting the Eurocentric bias of existing literature. Practically, it offers policymakers implications regarding sequencing, institutional pressure points, and evaluable reforms.

3. Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

3.1 Theoretical mechanism

The adoption of AI in regulatory enforcement alters three dimensions of the regulator-regulatee relationship, each corresponding to one of the assumptions identified in the previous section.

First, information asymmetry is inverted. In the traditional model, firms hold more information about their own activity than the regulator, making persuasion necessary as a cooperative information-extraction mechanism (Tombs and Whyte, 2013). AI systems trained on massive datasets can reverse this asymmetry. ARCA combines patrimonial, financial, and tax information in real time through the CEF System and General Resolution 5329 (Verrastro, 2025); Receita Federal cross-references more than forty databases; and Estonia's ETCB builds risk profiles visible to taxpayers. If the regulator can detect irregularities autonomously, the incentive to invest in persuasion declines.

Second, the locus of discretion is displaced. In traditional enforcement, the inspector exercises case-by-case discretion. With AI, discretion shifts from the inspector to the system designer (Coglianese and Lehr, 2017). Decisions become standardised but opaque, because the rules behind model outputs may be inscrutable even to those who deploy them.

Third, the logic of signalling is transformed. Scholz (1984) models enforcement as a repeated game in which firms adjust their behaviour by reading the regulator's signals. With algorithmic systems, firms must predict a model rather than interpret a human agent, opening space for algorithmic gaming.

These three shifts do not point in the same direction. Three competing hypotheses follow.

3.2 Hypotheses

H1 (deterrence hypothesis): AI adoption shifts the regulator toward the deterrence pole of the pyramid. If AI reduces the marginal cost of detection, preventive persuasion becomes less necessary. Expected observables include a higher audit-to-spending ratio, more frequent sanctions, and reduced advisory and educational outreach. The hypothesis captures the standard economics of enforcement and is consistent with concerns about expansive surveillance regimes (Tombs and Whyte, 2013).

H2 (selective persuasion hypothesis): AI adoption frees regulator capacity to invest in targeted persuasion, operationalising the responsive pyramid de facto. By automating the identification of high-risk firms, the regulator frees human resources for outreach to low-risk firms. Observables include bifurcation: more sanctions for high-risk firms and more education for low-risk ones. The hypothesis captures Coglianese's (2021) optimistic vision, although direct empirical evidence is weaker than for H1.

H3 (institutional mediation hypothesis): the effect of AI on enforcement posture is mediated by the strength of the institutional oversight framework. H3 is the central contribution of the work. Unlike H1 and H2, which derive from logics already articulated in the literature though not specifically applied to AI, H3 develops a mediation that existing literature has not thematised in this context. The argument is that the three shifts are plastic: they operate differently under different institutional constraints. Under robust oversight, AI tends to channel toward H2, because institutional controls limit drift toward purely punitive regimes. Under weak oversight, the same system may drift toward H1. The hypothesis draws by analogy on regulatory capitalism literature (Levi-Faur, 2005), which shows that different institutions produce different effects from similar regulatory inputs.

Table 1. Configuration of cases and their analytical role

Case	AI intensity	Institutional oversight	Analytical role
Argentina (ARCA)	High	Low	Contrasting case: high AI, weak oversight; key test for H1/H3.
Brazil (Receita Federal)	High	Medium	Intermediate case; Portaria 647/2026 tests oversight institutionalisation.
Estonia (ETCB)	High	High	High AI with strong oversight; long-term baseline.
Netherlands (post-2020)	Medium	Very high	Crucial H3 case after SyRI and post-2020 reconfiguration.

Ordinal categories (low, medium, high, very high) reflect each case's relative position in the set, supported by the sources documented in Section 4.

4. Data, Variables and Methods

4.1 Research design

This work adopts a comparative case-study design with within-case process tracing and structured cross-case comparison (George and Bennett, 2005; Yin, 2014). It does not aim at statistical causal inference: with N=4 there is no control of confounders or strict counterfactual. It produces analytical inference, meaning generalisation toward theory rather than toward the population. Control variables (economic size, tax pressure, administrative capacity, rule of law, legal tradition) are used not statistically but to support a controlled comparison in which variation in the dependent variable is plausibly linked to the independent variables rather than background heterogeneity.

The Netherlands operates as a crucial case (Collier, 2011): its oversight reached an extreme expression with the SyRI ruling, making it the strongest observational opportunity for H3. Argentina is a contrasting case: high AI intensity with emerging but weak oversight, where H1 should manifest clearly if it is correct. Brazil and Estonia provide intermediate gradations.

4.2 Cases

Argentina (ARCA, formerly AFIP). Intense AI deployment through multiple systems: SIPER (General Resolution 3985/2017) for risk profiling, the CEF System (General Resolution 4294/2018), APOC as a database of unreliable taxpayers, and General Resolution 5329/2023 for real-time control of VAT and Income Tax. Institutional oversight is weak but emerging: jurisprudence in Agraco and Andrada is beginning to limit the opacity of the CEF and automatic inclusion in APOC, though without the deterrent power of the Dutch SyRI ruling. The transition from AFIP to ARCA in October 2024, with an announced dismissal of 3,155 employees partially halted by the National Labour Court of Appeals in January 2025, makes this a natural experiment of recent opening.

Brazil (Receita Federal do Brasil). More than forty active AI projects, including ContÁgil, Projeto Farol, T-Cloud, and AJNA. Institutional oversight is intermediate: the LGPD (Law 13.709/2018) created a data-protection framework, and Portaria RFB 647/2026 institutionalises human-oversight safeguards, including a prohibition on autonomous algorithmic decisions and the creation of a Generative AI Curator role. The contrast with Argentina is informative: both are Latin American countries with comparable development but divergent institutional trajectories.

Estonia (Estonian Tax and Customs Board). Sustained ML deployment since around 2014 and robust oversight. The 2015 presidential veto of legislation on automatic invoice declaration, motivated by confidentiality concerns, illustrates the institutional restraint this work seeks to theorise. The enforcement culture incorporates transparency toward taxpayers through the visible Tax Behaviour Rating (Hadwick, n.d.).

Netherlands (Belastingdienst). High AI intensity pre-2020 and the most significant judicial intervention globally with the SyRI ruling (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, ECLI:NL:RBDHA:2020:1878).

The parallel toeslagenaffaire led to the resignation of the Rutte government and a €3.7 million fine by the Dutch Data Protection Authority.

4.3 Variables

Dependent variable: enforcement posture. Operationalised through four indicators: (a) the ratio of audits to advisory contacts; (b) the ratio of punitive sanctions to corrective actions; (c) discursive framing in official documents, especially the service/control semantic opposition; and (d) voluntary compliance rate. Sources include agency annual reports, the OECD Tax Administration Series for cross-country comparability, and content analysis of public communications such as taxpayer charters and policy speeches.

Primary independent variable (IV1): AI intensity. Classified qualitatively (low, medium, high) according to four criteria: (a) predictive models versus static rules; (b) coverage of enforcement decisions; (c) time since sustained implementation; and (d) system transparency.

Secondary independent variable (IV2): institutional oversight. Classified qualitatively (low, medium, high, very high) across four components: (a) effective power of the data-protection authority; (b) reach of judicial review of algorithmic decisions; (c) parliamentary scrutiny; and (d) specialised civil-society activity.

Control variables. Economic size (GDP), tax pressure, administrative capacity (Government Effectiveness from the World Bank), rule of law (WJP Rule of Law Index), and legal tradition.

The assignment of each case to an ordinal category is based on documentary evidence rather than impressionistic judgment. Table 2 synthesises the primary sources supporting the IV2 classification, the most sensitive variable for testing H3.

Table 2. Primary evidence supporting the institutional oversight (IV2) classification

Case	Classification	Main documentary evidence
Argentina	Low	AAIP with limited sanctions; Agraco and Andrada as isolated judicial interventions; episodic parliamentary scrutiny; civil society with limited influence; ARCA dismissals partly halted in January 2025.
Brazil	Medium	LGPD and operational ANPD; Portaria RFB 647/2026 requiring human oversight, prohibiting autonomous algorithmic decisions, and creating a Generative AI Curator; developing STJ jurisprudence; active civil society.
Estonia	High	2015 presidential veto as ex-ante control; AKI intervention record; documented transparency culture (Hadwick, n.d.).
Netherlands	Very high	SyRI ruling (ECLI:NL:RBDHA:2020:1878); €3.7 million AP fine; Rutte government's resignation over toeslagenaffaire; Ongekend Onrecht parliamentary report (2020).

Classification is the author's elaboration based on cited documentary evidence. It does not claim externally validated measurement but a structured ordering for comparison.

4.4 Data sources and analytical technique

Sources combine secondary quantitative data (OECD Tax Administration Series 2019 and 2022; CIAT for Latin America; World Bank), legal and regulatory documentation, academic literature, and semi-structured interviews with five informants per case across four profiles: agency officials, former inspectors with pre-AI experience, private-sector tax advisors, and representatives of civil society or DPAs. The former-inspector profile is especially valuable because it offers within-person observation of the displacement of discretion: someone who exercised case-by-case judgment before the system was introduced can articulate that shift better than any document.

The analysis proceeds in two steps. First, within-case process tracing reconstructs the causal chain between system adoption and changes in enforcement posture. Second, cross-case comparison applies identical structured questions. The Netherlands is a crucial test for H3: were H3 incorrect, high pre-2020 AI intensity should have consolidated a deterrence posture that the SyRI ruling only modulated; if H3 is correct, the ruling should have produced substantive reconfiguration toward selective persuasion.

4.5 Limitations

The design faces four limitations. Endogeneity: agencies with different enforcement cultures may self-select into AI adoption, mitigated by tracing the chronology of adoption. Algorithmic opacity: Argentine and Brazilian systems are partially classified, so the work relies on public documentation and rulings. Interviewee bias, mitigated by triangulation. The cross-sectional design captures a moment of transformation but not its full evolution. Given the scope of four national tax administrations, depth is also constrained: in execution, fieldwork would prioritise Argentina as contrasting case and the Netherlands as crucial case, with Estonia and Brazil as anchoring intermediate observations.

5. Conclusion

This work proposed a research design to examine how AI tools reshape the regulator-regulatee relationship. The central argument is that AI is not neutral with respect to enforcement posture: it displaces three assumptions of the classic model (informational asymmetry, locus of discretion, and signalling logic), and the net result depends on institutional oversight.

The comparative design allows three practical implications, each anchored in a case. These implications are the substantive contribution of the work for policymakers.

First, on sequencing. If H3 is correct, the optimal sequence is not to deploy AI and then build oversight, but the reverse. Middle-income countries that adopt intensive systems without first strengthening data-protection authorities, administrative courts, and algorithmic-audit frameworks risk consolidating deterrent postures. Argentina is the living example: ARCA advances with intensive AI while Agraco and Andrada are only beginning to establish limits.

Second, on institutional pressure points. The work identifies which institutions make a difference: judicial oversight with technical capacity, DPAs with effective sanctioning power, and documentary transparency. The Estonian case shows that an executive veto can be sufficient; the

Dutch case, that a judicial ruling can be; the Argentine case, that isolated jurisprudence without institutional backing is insufficient.

Third, on evaluable reforms. Brazil's Portaria 647/2026 is a natural experiment. If H3 is correct, Brazil should converge within five years toward a pattern closer to the Dutch model of selective persuasion. That is a falsifiable hypothesis for future research.

The findings extend beyond tax administration to domains where agencies use algorithmic tools to allocate enforcement attention, such as labour inspection and financial supervision. The relevant question for policymakers is not whether to adopt AI, but what institutional preconditions make adoption compatible with administrative effectiveness and the rule of law. A future agenda should add longitudinal studies and extend the framework to domains with less public transparency.

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